

1. Risk of integration with BrowserTAB plugins in hybrid development with Ionic
2. Risk of closing the notification cycle on Android Wear with PushNotification
3. Risk of TOC (Two Phase Commit) when using the Couchdb library in Android Studio
4. Failure with hotspots via third-party application
5. Loss of Xamarim configuration in versioning "build-tools" with Firebase
6. Loss of configuration when accessing microservices using Firebase authentication
7. Lack of clarity in the functionality of the services available
8. Lack of description of input and output data
9. Desired service not available
10. Desired service returns wrong information
11. Risk of connection failure when using Glide to view media on a hybrid server
12. Risk of recovering data stored in Mongo bank from a hybrid server
13. Loss of application connection in HTTP request via Postman using Retrofit
14. Loss of application connection when running animation on the device
15. Efficiency risk in operations with aligned vectors using Numpy
16. Loss of FTP connection via NodeJs on files stored using Mongoose
17. Risk of data scalability when using Retrofit through a REST Webservice
18. Loss of durability of data in microservices in access to BD with Mongoose
19. Memory overflow when uploading files (media) through REST webservice
20. Memory overflow using Kotlin coroutine in asynchronous tasks on the backend
21. Application compliance risk in places with organizational restrictions
22. Usability problem in the distribution of icons on the device screen
23. Security risk in offline persistence in hybrid development via Ionic Storage
24. Security risk with loss of encrypted data
25. Security flaw in decoding JSON tokens with JWT framework
26. Loss of Firebase authentication on Flutter with application in sandbox
27. Security risk in MainActivity using Facebook authentication by Firebase
28. Access to null objects in dynamic lists with Room library in Firebase
29. Efficiency risk in operations with aligned vectors using Numpy
30. Risk in the calculation of uncertainties of the model variables using Pandas
31. Low performance when using sockets in Firebase using listeners
32. Low performance in streaming communication via REST application
33. Memory overflow during application execution
34. Loss of data when querying the database
35. Failure to use IONIC to access media resources
36. Device geolocation treatment failed
37. Lack of accuracy in the predictive model
38. Loss of availability with Android Studio in offline tasks
39. Failed to access data stored in the cloud
40. Asynchronous image display error
41. Low performance in the display of media.